

CONDENSATION OF CHLORAL WITH 2-METHYL-4-QUINAZOLONE, 2-METHYL-3-AMINO-4-QUINAZOLONE AND SOME OF THEIR DERIVATIVES.

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Chloral condenses with 2-methyl-4-quinazolone and 2-methyl-3-amino-4-quinazolone giving rise in the former case to 2- γ -trichloro- β -hydroxypropyl-4-quinazolone. The hydroxy group appears to be very labile as it is eliminated as a molecule of water on further reactions. The γ -trichloromethyl group hydrolyses on treatment with alkali giving an acrylic acid derivative. 2-Methyl-3- β -trichloro- α -hydroxyethylamino-4-quinazolone eliminates water on treatment with acetyl chloride.

It is well known that a methyl group on a carbon atom, adjacent to the nitrogen atom of a basic heterocycle, as for instance in 2-methylpyridine, 2-methylquinoline, 4-methylquinoline and 2:4-dimethylquinoline etc. condenses with aliphatic aldehydes to form compounds of the type $R \cdot CH_2 \cdot CH \cdot OH \cdot R$ and with aromatic aldehydes to form compounds of the type $RCH_2 = CH \cdot R$.

An aliphatic aldehyde, such as chloral, has been condensed with 2-methylpyridine (Einhorn, *Annalen*, 1891, 265, 208), 2-methylquinoline (Miller and Spaddy, *Ber.*, 1855, 18, 3403), 4-methylquinoline (Königs and Muller, *Ber.* 1904, 37, 1337), and 2:4-dimethylquinoline (Königs and Mengel, *Ber.* 1904, 37, 1322), with a view to studying the products obtained by the alkaline hydrolysis of the γ -trichloromethyl group in the resulting compounds.

2-Methyl-4-quinazolone has been already condensed with aromatic aldehydes giving styryl compounds (Bogert and Beal, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 32, 1654; 1912 34, 516). On the other hand chloral forms with it the intermediate aldol type of condensation *viz.*, 2- γ -trichloro- β -hydroxypropyl-4-quinazolone (I).

(I)

(II)

The β -hydroxy group in 2- γ -trichloro- β -hydroxypropyl-4-quinazolone (I) readily eliminates as water, as on acetylation instead of giving the expected β -acetyl derivative it gives the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated compound (II). Similar tendency towards formation of $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturation was observed by Einhorn (*loc. cit.*) while preparing the β -chloro derivative of 2- γ -trichloro- β -hydroxypropylpyridine.

On treatment with concentrated caustic alkali the γ -trichloromethyl group in (I) hydrolyses to a carboxyl group with simultaneous elimination of a molecule of water and 4-quinazolone-2-acrylic acid (III) is obtained. Einhorn (*loc. cit.*), Miller and Spaddy (*loc. cit.*) and Königs and Mengel (*loc. cit.*) similarly obtained acrylic acid derivatives of pyridine, quinoline and 4-methylquinoline respectively, which on further oxidation gave the corresponding aldehydes.

It has been found that a primary aromatic amino group vigorously condenses with chloral with the formation of the compounds of the type $R'N=CH\cdot CCl_3$, and $(RNH)_2\cdot CHCCl_3$ according to the molecular proportion taken and no intermediate hydroxy compound could be isolated (Wheeler and co-workers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 30, 136). But 3-amino group in 2-methyl-3-amino-4-quinazolone exhibits a marked decrease in reactivity as chloral condenses with it to give the intermediate 2-methyl-3- β -trichloro- α -hydroxyethylamino-4-quinazolone (IV). Chloral could not be further condensed with the 2-methyl group due to the steric hindrance. On acetylation, the α -hydroxy group instead of forming the regular acetyl derivative eliminates water similarly giving 2-methyl-3-trichloroethylideneamino-4-quinazolone. The alkaline hydrolysis product of (IV) is under investigation.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

2- γ -Trichloro- β -hydroxypropyl-4-quinazolone. — 2-Methyl-4-quinazolone (10 g.) and chloral (10 g.) were heated in a flask, fitted with an air-condenser, on a wire-gauge over a low flame for 3 hours. On cooling, the mixture was poured into water and allowed to stand till the pasty mass solidified (15 g.). It crystallised from rectified spirit in shining yellow needles, m. p.

204-5°. It readily dissolves with decomposition in cold caustic alkali. It also dissolves in slightly warm dilute hydrochloric acid. It gives greenish fluorescence with dilute alcohol. (Found: C, 42.7; H, 2.9; N, 8.8; Cl, 34.53. $C_{11}H_8(O)_2N_2Cl_2$ requires C, 42.9; H 2.9; N, 9.1; Cl, 34.63 per cent). Hydrochloride of 2- γ -trichloro- β -hydroxy-4-quinazolone does not melt at 300°. (Found: Cl, 41.0. $C_{11}H_{10}(O)_2N_2Cl_4$ requires Cl, 41.2 per cent).

3:4-Dihydro-4-keto-2-quinazolinyl-trichloropropylene.—A mixture of the above compound (2 g.) and acetic anhydride (2 c.c.) to which one drop of concentrated sulphuric acid had been added was warmed in a test tube fitted with a condenser for 2 hours. On cooling, the mixture was poured into water, when a solid separated out. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid in white granules, m. p. 212°. It is insoluble in alkali and hydrochloric acid. (Found: Cl, 36.4. $C_{11}H_7ON_2Cl_3$ requires Cl, 36.8 per cent).

4-Quinazolone-2-acrylic acid.—2- γ -Trichloro- β -hydroxy-propyl-4-quinazolone (5 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide (10%, 50 c.c.) and the solution heated at 60° on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. On cooling it was neutralised to slight acidity by dilute acetic acid and the solution was concentrated to half the volume. The product crystallised on keeping in frigidaire in yellowish prismatic crystals, m. p. 262-63°. It is strongly acidic to litmus and gives effervescence with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution. (Found: C, 60.6; H, 3.9; N, 12.8. $C_{11}H_8(O)_2N_2$ requires C, 61.1; H, 3.7; N, 13.0 per cent).

2-Methyl-3- β -trichloro- α -hydroxyethylamino-4-quinazolone.—2-Methyl-3-amino-4-quinazolone (5 g.) and chloral (4 g.) were mixed together in a flask fitted with an air-condenser, when the mixture became hot. This mixture was heated on a water-bath at 70°-80° for 1 hour and on cooling, was poured into water. It crystallised from alcohol in white shining needles, m. p. 151-52°. (Found: N, 13.2; Cl, 33.3. $C_{11}H_{10}(O)_2N_2Cl_3$ requires N, 13.0; Cl, 33.0 per cent).

2-Methyl-3-trichloroethylideneaminoquinazolone.—2-Methyl-3- β -trichloro- α -hydroxyamino-4-quinazolone (1.5 g.) was dissolved in pyridine (10 c.c.) and acetyl chloride (2 c.c.) was added to it gradually at 0° with constant stirring. It was kept in a refrigerator overnight. Next day the solution was poured into dilute hydrochloric acid when a solid separated out. It crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m. p. 104°-5°. (Found: N, 13.8. $C_{11}H_8ON_2Cl_3$ requires N, 13.8 per cent).